

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING MEDICAL STUDENTS TO TRANSLATE SPECIALIST TEXTS FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK ON THE BASIS OF MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7766941>

Abstract: In this article, the methods of translating terms and official texts of medical students were discussed and several methods were implemented.

Key words: Texts, medical terminology, The values of the company, translation of the text, documents.

Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждались методы перевода терминов и официальных текстов студентов-медиков и было реализовано несколько методов.

Ключевые слова: Тексты, медицинская терминология, ценности компании, перевод текста, документов.

When it's a matter of learning, providing learners with a series of facts is not always sufficient. For students to efficiently understand their educational courses they need to be able to read around the subjects. To communicate properly people should be able to use their strongest language. This can be very complicated if most of your teachers speak different languages. Here comes the major importance of education translation.

As we have already said, translation is a means of communication. So, we have to deal with the process of translation in a very precise way. In other words, we, as translators and teachers as well, must be faithful to the original text. This is the simplest principle that should be taken into consideration in translation. But the translator may face problems through doing translation. The first problem is related to the reading and comprehension ability in the source language.

Before starting with the translation of the document, I conduct preliminary research about the company and the particular text. This includes, for example:

- The type of document
- Its purpose and target audience
- The values of the company
- The specific style and tone

This information is important to know the context of the document and also to keep the consistency among the different content of the same company. The more information I have available, the easier it is for me to properly adapt the text to be effective.

Translation of the text. Now it's time to deal with the text and start conveying the original message in the target language in a natural way. For ensuring higher quality, ideally, the translation should be done into the mother tongue of the translator; In this step, I solve the translation challenges arising from the text: specialised terminology, idioms, cultural references, source errors, abbreviations, etc. It's very important to have the original documents as a reference for taking into account the layout, images, etc.

For making the text as clear and specific as possible, I also research particular aspects of each project, such as the differences between financial products, details about the regulations and certain organisations in different countries, information about the locations mentioned or the products of the company to make marketing texts more attractive, etc. In case of doubt, I get in touch with the customer to confirm the information and to ensure that I take the right decisions.

Proofreading of the translation. Going over the whole text again improves the style. I make sure that the sentence structures are as clear and direct as possible (since, sometimes, there are too complex sentences that can be rewritten in a more natural style) and richer creative solutions or alternatives can emerge that better suit the context.

The goal is that the text reads as if it was directly written in Spanish, with the Spanish audience in mind. Furthermore, when the confidentiality agreements allow it, we perform this step between two persons, applying the so-called “four eyes” principle. We discuss each change, avoiding the introduction of errors during the proofreading step. This is an unusual added value in the industry because both steps are typically done separately. However, it’s difficult to detect the errors when rereading own texts, and many times errors are overlooked since one can even read what was intended to write instead of what’s actually written.

Spell check. Although it mostly just consists of adding words to the software dictionary and ignoring words that don’t have to be translated (like proper nouns, company names, or brands), this is a necessary step in the process of translation for ensuring that the text is free of typos.

Quality assurance. I use specific tools for performing the quality assurance (QA) and avoiding, among others:

- Numerical errors
- Inconsistencies
- Double spaces

Desktop publishing of the document. Once the text is extracted in its final format, I adapt the layout of the document to ensure that it’s similar to the original and even fix the errors that sometimes contains the source (e.g. non-uniform text alignments, the wrong numbering of the sections, headings of the same hierarchy level with different formatting, etc.). In this step, I also check the punctuation, line breaks, graphs, etc.

Final revision before submission. Finally, I verify that the whole text is correct in its final layout and that it stays true to the source.

I deliver the translated documents per email in editable files with a layout that respects to the utmost the original (that’s why it’s worthwhile to provide the text in editable format for its translation and also contributes to optimise the budget).

Of course, after all this process, I remain at the customer’s disposal for any inquiry about the delivered work. Additionally, in line with my commitment to sustainability, I don’t print any documents in the process of translation, avoiding unnecessary paper consumption.

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